

Biogenesis of antibacterial copper oxide nanoparticles synthesized from *Bacillus stratosphericus* BSM1 isolated from Mahabalipuram, Tamil Nadu

Akula Bhavya, Shanthi Kumari Kuthadi*, Dugyala Yogitha Bala

Department of Microbiology, Osmania University, Hyderabad, India

1. Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance has become a global challenge for the medical and research community. This study aims to investigate the antibacterial efficacy of biogenically synthesized copper nanoparticles (CuO NPs) derived from marine bacteria isolated from Mahabalipuram water resource, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Four distinct bacterial isolates were identified, encompassing *Bacillus stratosphericus* (BSM1) exhibiting the most promising antibacterial properties. The antibacterial activity of these copper oxide nanoparticles was evaluated against *Bacillus cereus*, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* using the Kirby-Bauer agar well diffusion method. The CuO NPs derived from BSM1 were further characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). This study highlights the potential of marine-derived compounds in combination with nanotechnology as a source of novel antibiotics and other compounds besides being a reliable approach for drug discovery. Further research is necessary to corroborate the findings against a broad spectrum of clinically relevant pathogens and to explore their ameliorative potential & mechanisms of action. These findings contribute to the research field in bringing novel antibiotics to light, thereby paving the way for future studies combating antibiotic resistance.

Keywords: Antibacterial activity, Nanotechnology, Copper Oxide nanoparticles, Marine bacteria, *Bacillus stratosphericus*

2. Introduction

Microorganisms produce antibiotics as secondary metabolites against bacterial infection in humans and animals. These antibiotics kill the bacteria by disrupting the cell wall and cell membrane or targeting DNA replication. Over a period, the overuse of drugs against pathogens

made them resistant to the drugs making them antibacterial resistant. Antibacterial resistance has become a challenge for the medical and research community [Dugyala, Y.B., and Kuthadi, S.K., 2024]. As the marine environment is known for its rich biodiversity, it produces novel antibiotics. These play a significant role in drug development and biomedicine [K.S. Shobhana, 2015].

Oceans cover over 70% of the earth's surface. The extreme habitat conditions, such as varying temperatures and salinity, produce diverse bioactive compounds, including antibiotics. These compounds are crucial for the organism's survival [Mohamed, S.S., et al., 2021]. Therefore, secondary metabolites have been reported to exhibit greater antibacterial activity and more effective therapeutic capabilities.

Nanoparticles for overcoming antibacterial resistance have been successful recently as they target biomolecules and regulate depletion and membrane interactions. Marine microbial community includes bacteria, fungi, viruses and other microorganisms. Bacterial nanoparticles known as nanomedicine, are used in curing various pathogenic infections and some tumour-associated cancers such as brain, lung, breast, and cardiovascular [Afzal, O., et al., 2022]. In 2016, the FDA approved nanomedicine as a therapeutic trait, as it is less harmful when compared to chemical-based therapies [Bobo, D., et al., 2016].

Nanoparticles are commonly known as solid, colloidal particles with sizes ranging from 1-100 nm. They are complex triple-layered surfaces, encompassing the surface layer, the shell and the core. Nanoparticles have unique properties, influenced by their size, shape, and environmental conditions. Other applications include their usage as fuel cells, organic pharmaceuticals, electronics optics, biosensors and various others. These nanoparticles can be produced by physical and chemical methods, but by methods, there are many drawbacks to the environment and are more cost-effective. Hence, nowadays, nanoparticles are produced through eco-friendly methods such as biosynthesis or green synthesis. Green synthesis of nanoparticles is a method for producing unalloyed, morphologically superior nanoparticles in a repeatable manner using biological materials as reducing and capping agents. This method is cost-effective, non-toxic and eco-friendly [Saba, H. 2015].

Much of the research work has been focused on gold, silver, and platinum metals in nanoparticle synthesis due to their high stability, easy chemical synthesis and broad

applications in cosmetics, medical applications and microelectronics. However, producing these nanoparticles is costly, and their use in the treatments may incur high expenses.

Among these metals, copper is stable, cheap, less toxic, and easily synthesized. Copper metals and copper metal oxides significantly affect pathogenic bacteria and are also used for cancer treatment. Exposure to CuO NPs reduces cell viability, increases lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and elevates levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and IL-8 dose independently [Jing, X., et al., 2015] [Mahmood, R.I., et al., 2022].

This study aims to investigate the antibacterial efficacy of marine bacteria using nanotechnology. Special focus is placed on synthesizing and characterizing nanoparticles derived from the metabolites of marine bacteria and their antibacterial activity against a range of clinically relevant bacterial pathogens.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Sample collection

Water samples were collected from the surface and depth of 10 km at Mahabalipuram sea level (**12.6165°N, 80.1993°E**) located in Chengalpattu district of Chennai, Tamil Nadu using sterile bottles and transported to the laboratory and stored at 4°C until further examination [Dugyala, Y.B., and Kuthadi, S.K., 2024].

3.2 Isolation of bacterial isolates

The collected water samples were subjected to serial dilution and a sample of 100 µL was inoculated onto plates containing sterile Zobell agar medium. These plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the isolates were selected and streaked to obtain pure cultures. For further analysis, these isolates were preserved as glycerol stocks at -80°C and slants at 4°C [Kumari, K.S. et al., 2020].

3.3 Morphological and biochemical profiling of bacterial isolate

Colony and cell morphology studies were performed based on their Gram's nature, shape, margin, arrangement and elevation of bacteria studied. For the taxonomic identification, different biochemical tests were performed for all the bacterial isolates following standard

protocols as stated in Bergey's manual and compared with a known type strain [Mandragutti, T., et al., 2021].

3.4 Effect of temperature and pH on isolates

The optimization studies on the growth of the bacterial isolates were carried out by Epoch ELISA reader at 600nm using 2 different parameters viz. Temperature (30°C,35°C,37°C) and pH (6,7,8). The collected data were used to plot graphs using MS Excel software [Vasavi, A., et al., 2024].

3.5 Determination of copper maximum tolerated concentrations [MTCs]

The copper tolerance of each bacterial isolate was assessed by streaking the isolate onto Luria Bertani (LB) agar medium containing increasing concentrations (0 to 6 mM) of CuSO₄.5H₂O (copper sulphate). These plates were incubated at 37°C and examined at regular intervals for up to 72 hours. The MTC values were recorded until no growth was observed on the plates after 3 days of incubation. All experimental setups were performed in triplicates [John, M.S. et al., 2021].

3.6 Biosynthesis of CuO nanoparticles

After determining the maximum tolerated concentrations, each bacterial isolate was inoculated into Luria Bertani medium (100 mL) with their respective concentration for the biosynthesis of CuO NPs at 37°C on a rotatory shaker (200 rpm). After 24 hours, CuSO₄.5H₂O was added to the microbial cell culture to a final concentration of 1 mM and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours on a rotatory shaker (150 rpm). For the control, LB medium with 1 mM CuSO₄ but without an organism was used. The change in colour of the solution from blue to dark green indicates the formation of NPs. This was recorded by absorption spectra in the wavelength of 200-800 nm at room temperature using Epoch ELISA [John, M.S. et al., 2021].

3.7 Purification/Refining of CuO NPs

After incubation, the culture was centrifuged at 5000 rpm at 4°C for 20min in Sorvall ST 16R centrifuge to separate the cell pellet from the cell-free supernatant. Nanoparticles were purified from both supernatant and pellet. To recover CuO NPs, present in the cell-free supernatant, the solution was centrifuged at 13,000 x g for 15 min in the same centrifuge. The pellet containing

the CuO NPs was washed with de-ionized water by repeated centrifuged steps [John, M.S. et al., 2021]. To recover NPs from the cell pellet, it was washed 3 times with de-ionized water to remove impurities and the unbound components. To prevent the oxidation of synthesized CuO NPs, they were re-dispersed in de-ionized water and stored at room temperature. Half of the solution was dried in the hot air oven at 60°C for the characterization [Hona, S. et al., 2019].

3.8 Antibacterial efficacy of copper oxide nanoparticles using Kirby-Bauer agar well diffusion method

Biosynthesized CuO NPs were examined for their antibacterial efficacy against test bacteria, using the agar well diffusion method. LB Agar media was used to grow clinically relevant test bacteria. 100 µL of the pathogenic cultures were spread onto agar plates and incubated in a refrigerator for 30 minutes. The wells were dug in the plates, loaded with 100 µL of CuO NPs and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Then, they were examined for inhibition zones and meticulously documented. This experiment was performed in triplicates [Bukhari, S.I., et al., 2021].

3.9 Characterization of CuO NPs

The shape and surface morphologies of biosynthesized nanoparticles were observed by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) by SEM-Zeiss EVO. The crystal structure of biosynthesized CuO NPs was determined by X-ray diffraction Analysis (XRD) using Rigaku Miniflex 600 X-ray Po. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is done for the detection of biomolecules and the interactions between the biomolecules and copper nanoparticles using Tensor 27 Bruker Optics Germany, CFRD. Analysis was carried out between the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ [Dulta, K., et al., 2022].

4. Identification of bacteria by 16S rRNA gene sequencing

Isolate with significant antibacterial activity among all the bacterial isolates tested was identified by 16S rRNA sequencing using 16S rRNA-F and 16S rRNA-R primers, and NCBI BLAST (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) was used to analyze the sequence resemblance to the species. PCR product of length 1500 bp purified and sequenced on ABI 370X1 Genetic Analyzer using the BDT v3.1 Cycle sequencing kit. The sequencing data was aligned and

analyzed to find the closest homologs for the microorganism. A phylogenetic tree was constructed using MEGA X software's neighbor joining method [Kimura, M., 1980].

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Isolation and characterization of bacterial isolates

Four different isolates with distinct morphology and characters were selected. They were labelled as BSM1, BSM2, BSM3, BSM4. Out of four, BSM3 and BSM4 were producing orange pigments. Similar bacterial separation techniques were employed to separate pigmented bacterial colonies from water samples from the Arabian Sea Coast in a work by Nikita, P., et al. (2020). Using conventional microbiological methods, the authors isolated nine pigmented bacterial colonies from the samples and described them according to physical and chemical characteristics. In another study by Devavani, K. and Umamaheswara Rao, V. (2024), similar methods were employed for isolating and characterizing the bacterial isolates.

Morphological characteristics	BSM1	BSM2	BSM3	BSM4
Colony morphology	Irregular	Circular	Circular	Circular
Margin	Entire	Entire	Entire	Entire
Pigmentation	Non-pigmented (white)	Non-pigmented (transparent)	Dark orange	orange
Elevation	Raised	Raised	Raised	Raised
Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Optical property	Opaque	Transparent	Opaque	Opaque
Gram Nature	Positive	Positive	Positive	Negative
Shape	Bacilli	Bacilli	Staphylococci	Clusters of cocci

Table 1 Morphological characteristics of the bacterial isolates

5.2 Biochemical characterization

Biochemical tests	BSM1	BSM2	BSM3	BSM4
Indole test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Methyl red test	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Voges-Proskauer test	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Citrate utilization test	Negative	Positive	Negative	Negative
Catalase test	Positive	Negative	Positive	Positive
Oxidase test	Negative	Positive	Positive	Positive

Table 2 Biochemical characteristics of the bacterial isolates

5.3 Effect of temperature and pH on bacterial isolates

Figure 1 Growth optimization of BSM1 at different temperatures and pH

Figure 2 Growth optimization of BSM2 at different temperatures and pH

Figure 3 Growth optimization of BSM3 at different temperatures and pH

Figure 4 Growth optimization of BSM4 at different temperatures and pH

5.4 Determination of copper maximum tolerated concentration

Copper tolerance for all the bacterial isolates was checked and bacterial growth assessment was performed for different CuSO4 concentrations.

Bacteria Isolates	0.0mM	1mM	2mM	3mM	4mM	5mM	6mM
BSM1	+++	+++	++	++	-	-	-

BSM2	+++	++	++	+	-	-	-
BSM3	+++	-	-	-	-	-	-
BSM4	+++	++	+	-	-	-	-

Table 3 MTC assay of bacterial isolates (High growth +++, medium growth++, low growth+, and no growth -).

Bacterial isolates	CuSO4(mM)
BSM1	3
BSM2	3
BSM3	0
BSM4	2

Table 4 MTC concentration of bacterial isolates

5.5 Biosynthesis of CuO NPs

All the bacterial isolates had shown different mM copper resistance, thus we concluded that these isolates may be able to synthesize copper NPs. Upon adding CuSO4 to the medium, a gradual transition in the colour of the solution was observed changing from blue to dark green for

hours.

Figure 5 Biosynthesis of CuO NPs (A)Control with LB 1mM (B) Biosynthesis of CuO NPs

5.6 Antibacterial efficacy of copper oxide nanoparticles

The antibacterial activity of CuO NPs was determined against clinically pathogenic bacterial strains. The appearance of clear zones indicates inhibition.

Test organism	BSM1	BSM2	BSM4
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	No activity	No activity	No activity
Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MRSA)	11mm	No activity	No activity
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	15 ± 0.2 mm	No activity	No activity
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	20 mm	No activity	No activity
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	18 ± 0.2 mm	No activity	No activity

Table 5 Antibacterial efficacy of nanoparticles against different clinically relevant test bacteria

The antibacterial activity of *Bacillus stratosphericus* (BSM1) against various pathogens, including Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, demonstrates its potential as an antibacterial agent. The recorded inhibition zones of 11 mm for MRSA, 15 mm for *Proteus vulgaris*, 20 mm for *Salmonella typhi*, and 18 mm for *Klebsiella pneumoniae* indicate a moderate level of efficacy, particularly significant in the context of rising antibiotic resistance.

The inhibition zone of 11 mm for MRSA by BSM1 is comparable to findings from studies on nanoparticle composites. For instance, Tariq, F., et al., (2020) reported silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) exhibiting inhibition zones of 4±0.09 mm against MRSA. Comparatively, a work reported by Swetha, S. and Valli, C.N., (2012) showcased that silver nanoparticles synthesized from

Bacillus cereus, have exhibited 15 mm and 14 mm of inhibition zones in diameter against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi*, respectively. 18 mm and 20 mm diameters of inhibition zones against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi* by BSM1 suggest strong and noteworthy antibacterial activity.

The antibacterial activity of *Bacillus stratosphericus* (BSM1) showcases its potential as an

antibacterial agent, particularly considering its moderate efficacy against MRSA, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Compared to various bacterial nanoparticle composites that exhibit lesser activity, BSM1 demonstrates competitive and, in some cases, superior antibacterial properties. This highlights the importance of exploring marine sources for developing effective antibacterial agents, especially in the face of increasing antibiotic resistance.

Figure 6 Antibacterial efficacy of BSM1 synthesized CuO nanoparticles against clinically relevant nanoparticles.

5.7 Characterization of CuO NPs

5.7.1 Ultraviolet-Visible Absorption Spectroscopy (UV)

The CuO NPs formation was primarily confirmed by the gradual change in the hue of the reaction mixture (blue to dark green). The UV-visible absorption spectrum of the biosynthesized CuO NPs showed a characteristic peak at 200-400 nm and an elevated peak at

230 nm which is typical for CuO NPs production (depicted in **Figure 6**). Similar peaks were reported by Amaliyah, S. et al., (2020).

Figure 6 Ultraviolet-visible absorption spectroscopy (UV)

5.7.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM analysis revealed the spherical shape of CuO NPs with an average size range of 20-50 nm (shown in **Figure 7**). Similar characteristics were revealed through SEM analysis reported by

Radhakrishnan, A. A., et al., (2014).

Figure 7 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of CuO NPs.

5.7.3 Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectroscopic analysis was performed for the identification of the functional groups present on the CuO NPs. The spectrum showed peaks at 3773 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 3359 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching), 1638 cm^{-1} (C=C stretching), and 618 cm^{-1} (CuO stretching). These peaks support the presence of monoclinic phase and no other IR active modes are observed in the range of $500 - 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which totally gives the existence of Cu_2O and also indicating the presence of proteins, polysaccharides, and other biomolecules that may have acted as capping and stabilizing agents for the nanoparticles (depicted in **Figure 8**). Similar peaks were reported

by Luna, I.Z., et al., (2015) and Mohamed EA. (2020).

Figure 8 Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

4.6.4 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

The XRD pattern of the CuO NPs exhibited distinct peaks at 2Θ at 35.5° , 38.7° , 48.8° , and 61.5° corresponding to the (002), (111), (202) and (311) planes of the face-centered cubic (FCC) structure of CuO, respectively (demonstrated in **Figure 9**). These intense and sharp peaks suggest that the synthesized CuO NPs were highly crystalline. Similar diffraction peaks were observed for synthesized CuO NPs at 2θ values of Bragg angle for 22.85° (020), 28.00° (021), 30.58° (110), 33.42° (002) 35.67° (111), 41.43° (131), 52.45° (113) and 59.16° (200) in a study

reported by Keabadile, O.P., et al., (2020).

Figure 9 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

5.8 Identification using 16S rRNA gene-based molecular method

Among the bacterial isolates, BSM1 has shown better activity when compared to other bacterial isolates. Therefore, identification was done using 16S rRNA gene sequencing. This revealed BSM1 as *Bacillus stratosphericus*. The phylogenetic analysis of BSM1 is shown in **Figure 10**. The 16S rRNA gene sequence was submitted to the Gene Bank (NCBI) and accession number

PQ160461 was received.

Figure 10 Evolutionary analysis and phylogenetic tree of BSM1 using Maximum Likelihood method.

6. Conclusion

To conclude, the study identified four distinct bacterial isolates, namely BSM1, BSM2, BSM3, and BSM4 from a water sample collected from Mahabalipuram, Chennai, Tamil Nadu,

exhibiting antibacterial efficacy and potential for pharmaceutical applications. The biosynthesis of CuO NPs using marine bacterial isolates, particularly *Bacillus stratosphericus* strain BSM1, exhibits significant potential in addressing the rising challenge of antibacterial resistance. This research corroborates findings from various sources that spotlight the efficacy of biogenic nanoparticles in therapeutic applications by underscoring the importance of exploring marine-derived compounds for the synthesis of nanoparticles, as they proffer an eco-friendly and sustainable alternative to conventional chemical synthesis methods. This serves as a promising avenue in the development of novel antibacterial agents. However, continued research is essential for exploring the therapeutic efficacy of these nanoparticles against a broader spectrum of clinically relevant pathogens, as well as investigating their modes of action in greater detail.

7. Acknowledgement

We express our gratitude to the Marine Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Microbiology, Osmania University, Hyderabad for providing the necessary laboratory facility for this study.

8. Conflict of Interest

We declare no conflict of interest.

9. References

1. Dugyala, Y. B., and Kuthadi, S. K. (2024). Antibacterial Activity of *Micrococcus luteus* YSD1 Isolated from Velankanni Water Source, Tamil Nadu. In Department of Microbiology, Osmania University, Hyderabad, India, *Acta Scientific Biotechnology* (Vol. 5, Issue 2, pp. 26–33). <https://actascientific.com/ASBT/pdf/ASBT-04-0201.pdf>
2. K. S. Sobhana (2015). Marine Biodiversity Division, Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute, Kochi-682 018 https://eprints.cmfri.org.in/10431/1/27_Sobhana_KS.pdf
3. Mohamed, S. S., Abdelhamid, S. A., and Ali, R. H. (2021). Isolation and identification of marine microbial products. *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 19(1), 162. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00259-3>
4. Afzal, O., Altamimi, A. S. A., Nadeem, M. S., Alzarea, S. I., Almalki, W. H., Tariq, A., Mubeen, B., Murtaza, B. N., Iftikhar, S., Riaz, N., and Kazmi, I. (2022). Nanoparticles in drug

delivery: From history to therapeutic applications. *Nanomaterials*, 12(24), 4494. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12244494>

5. Bobo, D., Robinson, K. J., Islam, J., Thurecht, K. J., and Corrie, S. R. (2016). Nanoparticle-Based Medicines: A review of FDA-Approved materials and clinical trials to date. *Pharmaceutical Research*, 33(10), 2373–2387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-016-1958-5>

6. Saba Hasan 2015. A Review on nanoparticles: Their synthesis and types. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 4, 1-3. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Saba-Hasan/publication/273203342_A_Review_on_Nanoparticles_Their_Synthesis_and_Types/link/s/54fb49ff0cf270426d0dcb29/A-Review-on-Nanoparticles-Their-Synthesis-and-Types.pdf?utm_medium=email&utm_source=transaction

7. Jing, X., Park, J. H., Peters, T. M., and Thorne, P. S. (2015). Toxicity of copper oxide nanoparticles in lung epithelial cells exposed at the air-liquid interface compared with in vivo assessment. *Toxicology in Vitro*, 29(3), 502–511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2014.12.023>

8. Mahmood, R. I., Kadhim, A. A., Ibraheem, S., Albukhaty, S., Mohammed-Salih, H. S., Abbas, R. H., Jabir, M. S., Mohammed, M. K. A., Nayef, U. M., AlMalki, F. A., Sulaiman, G. M., and Al-Karagoly, H. (2022). Biosynthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles mediated *Annona muricata* as cytotoxic and apoptosis inducer factor in breast cancer cell lines. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-20360-y>

9. Kumari, K. S., Shivakrishna, P., Al-Attar, A. M., and Ganduri, V. R. (2020). Antibacterial and cytotoxicity activities of bioactive compounds from *Micrococcus* species OUS9 isolated from seawater. *Journal of King Saud University - Science*, 32(6), 2818–2825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2020.07.003>

10. Mandragutti, T., Dokka, M. K., Panchagnula, B., and Godi, S. (2021b). Molecular characterization of marine bacterial isolates of Visakhapatnam coast—efficacy in dye decolourization and bioremediation of cadmium. *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 19(1), 87. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-021-00189-0>

11. Kumari, S., Angeri, V., and Yogitha Bala, D., Department of Microbiology, Osmania University, India. (2024). Isolation and Molecular Characterization of a Bacteria VSB3 from the Marine Environment and its Antibacterial Activities. In *Acta Scientific Biotechnology* (Vol. 5, Issue 3) [Research Article]. <https://actascientific.com/ASBT/pdf/ASBT-04-0204.pdf>
12. John, M. S., Nagoth, J. A., Zannotti, M., Giovannetti, R., Mancini, A., Ramasamy, K. P., Miceli, C., and Pucciarelli, S. (2021b). Biogenic Synthesis of Copper Nanoparticles Using Bacterial Strains Isolated from an Antarctic Consortium Associated to a Psychrophilic Marine Ciliate: Characterization and Potential Application as Antimicrobial Agents. *Marine Drugs*, 19(5), 263. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md19050263>
13. Hona, S., Dangol, R., Ghatane, J., Giri, D., and Pradhananga, R. R. (2019). Antimicrobial effect of copper nanoparticles synthesized by chemical method. *International Journal of Applied Sciences and Biotechnology*, 7(4), 421–428. <https://doi.org/10.3126/ijasbt.v7i4.26295>
14. Bukhari, S. I., Hamed, M. M., Al-Agamy, M. H., Gazwi, H. S. S., Radwan, H. H., and Youssif, A. M. (2021). Biosynthesis of Copper oxide nanoparticles using streptomyces MHM38 and its biological applications. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 2021, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6693302>
15. Dulta, K., Ağçeli, G. K., Chauhan, P., Jasrotia, R., Chauhan, P. K., and Ighalo, J. O. (2022). Multifunctional CuO nanoparticles with enhanced photocatalytic dye degradation and antibacterial activity. *Sustainable Environment Research*, 32(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42834-021-00111-w>
16. Kimura, M. (1980). A simple method for estimating evolutionary rates of base substitutions through comparative studies of nucleotide sequences. *Journal of Molecular Evolution*, 16(2), 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01731581>
17. Patel, N., Dwivedi, M., Jadeja, S., and Begum, R. (2020). Antibacterial Activity of Marine Bacterial Pigments Obtained from Arabian Sea Water Samples. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, 14(1), 517–526. <https://doi.org/10.22207/jpam.14.1.54>

18. Tariq, F., Ahmed, N., Afzal, M., Khan, M. A. U., and Zeshan, B. (2020). Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of *Bacillus subtilis*-derived silver nanoparticles against Multidrug-Resistant bacteria. *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology*, 13(5). <https://doi.org/10.5812/jjm.91934>
19. Sunkar S, and Nachiyar CV. Biogenesis of antibacterial silver nanoparticles using the endophytic bacterium *Bacillus cereus* isolated from *Garcinia xanthochymus*. *Asian Pac J Trop Biomed*. 2012 Dec;2(12):953-9. PMID: 23593575; PMCID: PMC3621471. [https://doi.org/10.1016%2FS2221-1691\(13\)60006-4](https://doi.org/10.1016%2FS2221-1691(13)60006-4)
20. Amaliyah S, Pangesti DP, Masruri M, Sabarudin A, and Sumitro SB. Green synthesis and characterization of copper nanoparticles using *Piper retrofractum* Vahl extract as bioreductor and capping agent. *Heliyon*. 2020 Aug 7;6(8): e04636. PMID: 32793839; PMCID: PMC7415843. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04636>
21. Radhakrishnan, A. A., and Beena, B. B., Nanoscience Research Lab. (2014). Structural and optical absorption analysis of CUO nanoparticles. In *Indian Journal of Advances in Chemical Science* (Vol. 2, Issue 2, pp. 158–161). <https://www.ijacskros.com/artcles/IJACS-M64.pdf>
22. Luna, I. Z., Hilary, L. N., Chowdhury, A. M. S., Gafur, M. A., Khan, N., and Khan, R. A. (2015). Preparation and characterization of copper oxide nanoparticles synthesized via chemical precipitation method. *OALib*, 02(03), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1101409>
23. Mohamed EA. Green synthesis of copper & copper oxide nanoparticles using the extract of seedless dates. *Heliyon*. 2020 Jan 30;6(1): e03123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e03123>
24. Keabadile, O. P., Aremu, A. O., Elugoke, S. E., and Fayemi, O. E. (2020). Green and Traditional Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles—Comparative Study. *Nanomaterials*, 10(12), 2502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10122502>
25. Devavani, K., & Rao, V. U. (2024). Isolation, Screening and Identification of Marine bacteria for their Potential Bioactivity. *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences*. <https://www.ajbls.com/article/2024/13/2/551-560>